

3rd Hanrahan Lecture

HOW GEOTECHNICAL DESIGN HAS ADVANCED IN IRELAND AND EUROPE WITH EUROCODE 7

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Eurocode 7 Committee meeting at Engineers Ireland in January 1983

SYNOPSIS

This paper describes how geotechnical design in Ireland and Europe has advanced with Eurocode 7 during the past 40 years. The situation in Ireland and Europe regarding geotechnical design and the political framework when work started on Eurocode 7 in 1981 are presented. The development of regulations and standards for geotechnical design, including the formation and role of NSAI is explained. The Irish involvement in Eurocode7 began following the formation of the Geotechnical Society of Ireland in 1978 with the appointment in 1981 of an Irish representative to the committee preparing a Model Code for Eurocode 7. This led to the hosting in Dublin of the IX ECSMFE in 1987 with the theme *Groundwater Effects in Geotechnical Engineering*. How groundwater should be treated in geotechnical design has remained a challenge for those drafting Eurocode 7. Other challenges have included harmonising it with the other Eurocodes for structural design and accommodating the different geotechnical design traditions in Europe. These challenges were overcome and Eurocode 7 was eventually implemented in 2010. Now, after being used for 10 years, a second generation of Eurocode 7 is being prepared. The aims and main features of the next version of Eurocode 7 are outlined, including its improved ease of use and how it is honing the safety and reliability aspects of geotechnical design.

1. SITUATION PRIOR TO EUROCODE 7

1.1 Geotechnical Design in 1981

To understand how geotechnical design has advanced in Ireland and Europe with Eurocode 7, it is necessary to examine the situation regarding geotechnical engineering in Ireland and Europe before work on Eurocode 7 started in 1981. There were no Irish standards for geotechnical design and Ireland did not have a dedicated national standards body. In Ireland the responsibility for standards functions in construction was shared by a number of organisations including:

- Institute for Industrial Research and Standards (IIRS)
- An Foras Forbartha, The National Institute for Physical Planning and Construction Research

The periods when different Irish bodies had a function for Irish standards were:

- IIRS from 1946
- Eolas from 1988
- Forfás from 1994 to 2014.

Geotechnical design in Ireland was carried out mainly using the relevant codes of practice published by the British Standards Institution (BSI), with separate codes for different geotechnical structures, reports published by technical bodies or research institutions and papers by respected geotechnical engineers. Examples of codes of practice used by Irish geotechnical engineers include *CP 2004: Code of Practice for Foundations* (BSI, 1972), which was used for the design of spread and pile foundations and caissons, and *CP 2: Earth retaining structures* (IStructE, 1951), which was for the design of retaining walls.

These codes were based on the use of overall factors of safety and permissible stresses. They provided much general advice on the geotechnical design and construction. However, they provided no requirements, only recommendations, since the operative verb used in these standards was “should” not “shall” or “must”. Very little guidance was provided on the level of safety required and no advice was provided on how to selection the values of the ground parameters for use in design calculations and how cautious they should be. In the case of foundations on cohesive soils, CP 2004 stated that “to ensure safety against shear failure, the ultimate bearing capacity should be divided by an overall factor of safety, conventionally of the order of 2 or 3”. In the case of non-cohesive soils, it stated that “for very narrow foundations the design is likely to be governed by the need for an adequate factor of safety against shear failure” but no guidance was given. Also no guidance at all was given on the magnitude of the factor of safety in the case of foundations on cohesionless soils.

in 1981. In western Europe, most countries had their own different standards for geotechnical designs reflecting national practice and ground conditions. All except the Danish code were based on global factors of safety and permissible stresses.

A source of information about the properties of Irish soils,

Figure 1: Hanrahan booklet on Irish Glacial Till

frequently referred to by Irish geotechnical engineers in 1981, was the booklet by Professor Eamon Hanrahan, *Irish Glacial Till: Origin and characteristics*, published by An Foras Forbartha (Hanrahan, 1979). The cover of this booklet is shown in Figure 1. This booklet provided much helpful information and data about Irish glacial soils and correlations to determine their properties. Another paper commonly referred to in 1981, and still referred to today, to determine the undrained shear strength of Dublin Boulder Clay, is the paper by Stroud (1975) The standard penetration test and the engineering properties of glacial materials

1.2 Bye-Laws for construction

The only regulations relating to geotechnical works in Ireland prior to 1981 were the Bye-Laws for the construction, conversion and alteration of buildings published by: Dublin City Council, Cork County Council and Dun Laoghaire Corporation. The Bye Laws published by the three corporations were all brief and similar documents, for example the Dublin Corporation's Bye Laws were in an A5 booklet with just 76 A5 pages covering all the safety and health aspects relating to the construction of buildings. The text in both the Dublin City Council Bye-Laws, which were published in 1949, see Figure 2, and in the Dun Laoghaire Corporation Bye-Laws, which were published in 1959, was identical except that the Dublin Bye-Laws refer to the City Architect or Building Surveyor while the Dun Laoghaire bye-laws refer to the Borough Surveyor.

Regarding foundations, both the Dunlin and Dun Laoghaire Bye-Laws stated in Clause 12 that: “Every foundation shall rest on suitable ground and shall be constructed to sustain and transmit safely all the loading

Figure 2: Corporation of Dublin Bye-Laws, 1949

imposed thereon.” However, no definition was given of what “*suitable ground*” is or how the requirement to “*transmit safely all the loading imposed*” should be achieved. Verification of this requirement was through inspection by the Local Authority since Clause 109(1) in the Dublin Bye-Laws stated: “*Every person who shall proceed to erect any building or otherwise execute any work to which any of the foregoing bye-laws apply shall give to the City Architect or Building Surveyor at least two clear days’ notice in writing of the date on which the erection of the building or the execution of the work will be commenced, and such person shall also, before proceeding to cover up any drain or fill any foundation, give to the City Architect or Building Surveyor/Borough Surveyor at least two clear days’ notice in writing of the date on which the covering up of such drain or the filling in of such foundation will be commenced*”.

1.3 Geotechnical Society of Ireland

Until 1977 there was no professional body in Ireland specifically for geotechnical engineers. The Irish National Society of the International Society for Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering (ISSMFE) was hosted by the Institution of Engineers of Ireland (IEI), which paid the annual subscription to the ISSMFE, and returned a list of members to the ISSMFE. However, the Irish Society was not active and, in 1977, Matt O’Donovan, Secretary of the IEI, noted that, contrary to the general trend throughout the world, the membership of the Irish National Society was falling. To reverse the falling membership trend, Matt O’Donovan called a meeting of geotechnical engineers in the IEI on 23 November 1977 with a view to the formation of an Irish geotechnical society. This

meeting was chaired by Professor Hanrahan from UCD and those present included Professor Reg Kirwan from TCD and a number of geotechnical engineers from practice and academia. The meeting decided the first step was to form a committee with Frank Motherway from the IIRS as chairman and Eric Farrell as secretary. The other members of the committee were S Davitt, E Farrell, M Grace T Orr, J Sheedy and T Widdis. Professors Hanrahan and Kirwan decided not to become involved in the new society but to leave it to younger geotechnical engineers.

At the subsequent meeting of the committee at the IEI on 1 December 1977 it was agreed to establish the Geotechnical Society of Ireland as a society within the IEI. It was agreed that the aims of the Society should be “*The promotion of co-operation among engineers and scientists for the advancement of knowledge in the field of geotechnical engineering and allied fields*”. Regarding the criteria for membership it was agreed that “*Individual membership shall be open to those actively engaged or otherwise interested in work lying within the scope of the Society, upon payment of the appropriate entrance fee and annual subscription*”. During 1978 the foundation of the Geotechnical Society of Ireland were laid by defining its objectives, drafting a constitution, recommending forms of membership and annual subscriptions, and organizing two public meetings. Initially the IEI had a problem with non IEI members being members of the Geotechnical Society. However, a resolution to that issue was found whereby the Society was part of the IEI yet could have members who were not members of the IEI.

The first public meeting was a panel discussion on “*Site Investigation Methods*” led by M. Grace and F. Motherway on 30 January 1978 and had an attendance of 49, which was very encouraging and demonstrated the general interest in geotechnics in Ireland. The second meeting was a lecture on “*Geophysical Methods in Civil Engineering*” by B Williams on 30 October 1978. By the time the IEI next had to submit a list of members of the Irish National Society to the ISSMFE it submitted a list of 73 members, a dramatic increase on the situation before the formation of the Geotechnical Society of Ireland.

1.4 Political Situation in Europe and Ireland

Politically in 1981 Europe was divided into two zones, east and west, by the “*Iron Curtain*” with little communication and great restrictions on travel between the two zones. In the west, in 1973, Ireland, the UK and Denmark joined Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg and The Netherlands as members of which of the European Economic Community (EEC), see Figure 3, also known as the Common Market, which was the precursor to the European Union (EU) Economic Community (EEC, which was the precursor to the European Union. Greece joined the EEC in 1981, making 10 the number of states in the EEC 10 at that time, see Figure 3, before Spain and Portugal joined in 1985.

Monetarily in Ireland, up to 1977, there was a one-to-one link between the Irish pound and pound sterling. However, the link with sterling was broken in 1977 when

Figure 3: 10 States of EEC in 1981

Ireland joined the European Monetary System (EMS) while the UK did not

2. START OF EUROCODE 7

2.1 The Eurocodes

In 1974 a number of European universities and representatives of the engineering profession decided to prepare harmonised European standards for structural design based on the limit state design method. Then, in 1975 the Commission of the EEC decided on an action programme in the field of construction based on the Treaty of Rome with the objective being the elimination of technical obstacles to trade and the harmonization of technical specifications within the EEC member states. Within this action programme the European Commission established the Eurocodes as a set of harmonised technical rules for the design of construction works which would initially serve as an alternative to the national rules in the EEC members states and ultimately would replace them. The European Commission decided to link up with and support the initial work that had started on the preparation harmonised European standards so that, from the start, the Eurocodes were based on the limit state design method.

2.2 Eurocode 7

In 1980 the committee of European Commission responsible for the Eurocodes was planning to draft Eurocode 7 for geotechnical design but, unlike for the other Eurocodes, there was no model limit state geotechnical design code to start from. Professor Kevin Nash, Secretary General of the ISSMFE, who was a Professor at King's College London and also a graduate of TCD with Irish roots, wrote to the Eurocode committee saying the ISSMFE was "*keenly interested*" in drafting a model code for Eurocode 7 and reviewing the geotechnical design practice in Europe. He stated that the ISSMFE considered "*it is important that Eurocode 7 is established as a flexible code in order to take the large differences in the physical environments within the area of the Community into account, and also in order to allow*

the future scientific development of foundation engineering in Europe" In writing this statement he was correctly anticipating some of the challenges that would arise in the development of Eurocode 7 and the eventual form of Eurocode 7.

The Commission accepted the offer from Professor Nash to establish an ISSMFE committee to prepare a model code for Eurocode 7. In 1980 Professor Nash wrote to the national geotechnical societies of the 9 EEC member states plus Greece (due to join in 1981) inviting them to nominate a representative to the ISSMFE committee to prepare a model code for Eurocode 7. The GSI committee received this letter and Trevor Orr was chosen to be the Irish representative on the Eurocode 7 Model Code committee. Professor Niels Krebs Ovesen from Denmark was appointed chair of this committee. It was very appropriate that Professor Krebs Ovesen was appointed chair of the committee because, at that time Denmark was the only EEC country with a limit state geotechnical design code and hence there was very little experience in Europe of limit state design in geotechnics. After initial meetings, first in Brussels in April 1981 and then during the International Conference of the ISSMFE in Stockholm in June 1981, the first working meeting of the model code committee was held in Paris in May 1982. Subsequent meetings were held in different EC member countries.

Professor Nash died suddenly, aged 59, in April 1981 and Professor John Burland acted as secretary general of the ISSMFE for a short period until R Parry was appointed in 1981. In 1982 the new president of the ISSMFE, Victor de Mello, who was elected at the conference in Stockholm, decided it was not appropriate for the ISSMFE to be involved in standards preparation and hence withdrew the ISSMFE support for the Eurocode 7 committee, which therefore became an "ad hoc" committee. There was no EU or national financial support for members to attend meetings hence the GSI had to raise funds from consultants and contracts to support Trevor Orr's attendance at Eurocode committee meetings. When work started on the Eurocodes it was before the advent of Ryanair and low cost airlines. it was cut price airline. Hence Trevor Orr took the "magic bus" from Dun Laoghaire to Paris, a gruelling journey involving two ferry crossings and two bus journeys, one across Wales and England and another across the north of France. Fortunately funds were raised so that subsequent meetings were attended by plane and the magic bus was not used again.

Professor Bengt Broms became president of the ISSMFE from 1985 to 1989. Under his presidency the ISSMFE changed its name to the International Society for Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering, i.e. ISSMGE. In addition Professor Broms brought in a change in policy with regard to involvement of the international society with standards so that it was now considered appropriate that the ISSMGE should become involved in the development of standards. Unfortunately, this change in policy was too late to affect the status of the Model Code Committee, which remained an ad hoc committee. However, it did affect the activities of the ISSMGE as its

Figure 4: Model Code committee at work

Figure 5: Crack cause by heave in a house in Spain

first conference session on geotechnical design codes was held at the international conference in Rio de Janeiro in 1989. Since then the ISSMGE has actively supported the development of codes for geotechnical design and has established committees concerned with code evaluation and with safety in geotechnical design: e.g.

- ERTC 10 Evaluation of Eurocode 7
- TC205 Safety and serviceability in geotechnical design.

The Model Code committee was working at a time before laptop computers and the internet were available. Hence hard copies of documents were used and these were exchanged by post or by fax. This is evident from the photograph of the committee at work in Figure 4. When Model Code committee meeting were held in the different countries, local examples of geotechnical interest were visited. Figure 5 shows a crack in a building in Seville, Spain caused by heave of expansive soil.

A meeting of the Model Code committee was held in Dublin in Dublin at the IEI on 14-15 January 1983. Those attending are shown in the photo in Figure 6 taken on the steps of 22 Clyde Road. The grand-daughter, Constance Heijnen, of Wim Heijnen, the Dutch member, drew the cartoon of the group shown in Figure 7. The difference between the two photographs is that the first one was taken by a representative from the European Commission, who attended the meeting to monitor what we were doing. He is shown in the cartoon in place of Eric Farrell, who took the photograph from which the cartoon was drawn. Note that N Krebs Ovesen is given a flag with the letter S, indicating Sweden, although he actually came

Figure 6: Ad hoc Model Code committee meeting at the IEI, Dublin, January 1983

Front row: Trevor Orr (Ireland), Demetrios Coumoulos (Greece), Niels Krebs Ovesen (Denmark), Wim Heijnen (Netherlands)

Middle row: Willie Sadgorski (Germany), Terry Thorpe (representing Prof Smoltczyk, Germany), Eric Farrell (Ireland)

Back Row: Brian Simpson (UK), Emanuel Lousberg (Belgium), Francois Baguelin (France), Rudgiero Japelli (Italy), Henk Nelissen (Netherlands)

Figure 7: Cartoon of the Ad hoc Model Code committee

from Denmark, and Thorpe, an Englishman, is given a flag with the letter D indicating Germany because he was representing Professor Smoltczyk from Germany.

The model code committee completed its work in 1987 and submitted a model code to the EC. The EU then agreed to sponsor work on the preparation of the next stage which was an ENV (trial) version of Eurocode 7. Orr (2008) has provided more information about the development of Eurocode 7 from its start in 1980 with the appointment of Niels Krebs Ovesen as chair of the model code committee through to the publication of the current EN, i.e. full standard version of Part 1 in 2004 and Part 2 in 2007.

2.3 9th European Conference of the ISSMFE

Largely as a result of contacts established in Europe through involvement in Eurocode 7, the Geotechnical Society of Ireland put in a successful bid to host the 9th European Conference of ISSMFE, i.e. the IX ECSMFE. This Conference was held in Trinity College Dublin and in the

Figure 8: Cover of Volume 1 of IX ECSMFE proceedings

National Concert Hall on 2-5 September 1987, 10 years after the decision to form the Geotechnical Society of Ireland. The conference organising committee consisted of Bill Quinn (chair), Eric Farrell (treasurer), Trevor Orr (secretary), John Higgins, Martin Grace and Tom Widdis.

The IX ECSMFE was very successful, with 491 delegates and 150 accompanying persons, and it made a sizeable profit. Part of the profit from the conference was used to establish the Geotechnical Trust Fund of the Institution of Engineers of Ireland with the following objectives:

- To support research in geotechnics in Ireland through the granting of awards to postgraduate students to carry out research leading to MSc or PhD degrees in geotechnical engineering at a university w
- Provided funds are available, to provide grants to students and young geotechnical engineers to attend the Young Geotechnical Engineers Conferences.

For many years, the Trust Fund supported geotechnical research in Irish universities before state funding became available. It has turned out that the majority of geotechnical lecturers in Irish universities today received awards from the Geotechnical Trust Fund to support their PhD research.

The theme chosen for the IX ECSMFE was *Groundwater effects in Geotechnical Engineering*. This theme was timely because, as noted earlier, how to handle groundwater effects was one of the challenges posed for those drafting Eurocode 7. Professor Hanrahan was one of the editors of the Proceedings volumes of the IX ECSMFE as can be seen from the cover of Volume 1 shown in Figure 8. He also presented one of the three invited special lectures, which was entitled: “*Drainage,*

groundwater lowering and consolidation” (Hanrahan, 1979). Another special lecture was Nash Lecture, named in honour of Professor Kevin Nash, presented by Professor Burland on the “*The teaching of soil mechanics: A personal view*” (Burland, 1979) , which has been very influential, particularly in the academic geotechnical community, and has been frequently referenced.

3. CHALLENGES AND BENEFITS OF EUROCODE 7

3.1 Nature of the Eurocodes

The Eurocodes were conceived as a harmonised set of standards for the design of structures using different materials. Separate Eurocodes were prepared for designs using the different materials, e.g. concrete, steel, timber, masonry and soil and rock. A head Eurocode was prepared with the general design rules to be adopted by the harmonised Eurocode for each material and a separate Eurocode was prepared for the loads (called actions) acting on structures. The design philosophy adopted was the limit state design method with partial factors applied to representative actions and characteristic material properties. Designs to the Eurocodes aim to achieve structures with a particular target level of reliability, i.e. with an acceptably low probability of failure.

3.2 Features of soil and challenges for Eurocode 7

The components involved in geotechnical and structural design are the same. However, while Eurocodes are a harmonised set of standards for structural and geotechnical design, geotechnical design differs from structural design due to the following features of soil which the materials used for structural design, such as steel, either do not have or only have to a much lesser extent:

1. Natural material
2. Particulate and hence frictional material
3. 2- or 3-phases
4. Wide range of particle sizes hence time-dependent behaviour
5. Variable
6. Non-homogeneous
7. Ductile
8. Dilatant
9. Compressible with low shear stiffness
10. Non-linear and complex stress-strain behaviour.

These features of soil have presented the drafters of Eurocode 7 with a number of challenges, particularly since Eurocode 7 was intended to be one of a suite of Eurocodes all with the same basis of design set out in the head Eurocode. The consequences for Eurocode 7 of the challenges posed by each of these special features of soil has been explained by Orr (2012) and are summarised in Table 1.

3.3 Characteristic value of a geotechnical parameter

The Eurocodes are a harmonised set of standards, but the definition of the characteristic value of a material property as a particular fractile of an infinite test series was not appropriate for geotechnical design. Hence, in order to harmonise Eurocode 7 with the other Eurocodes,

Feature of soil	Consequences for Geotechnical Design
1 Natural material	Properties are determined, not specified, so ground investigation and testing are part of design process. Hence need for EN 1997-2: Ground investigation and testing.
2 Particulate	Frictional behaviour – so strength depends on normal stress. Need care factoring loads as they are unfavourable when acting as loads but favourable when contributing to resistance.
3 2 or 3 phase material	Soil behaviour is function of effective stress since mineral particles have shear strength while water and air have no shear strength. Principle of effective stress needs to be taken into account. Two additional limit states relating to groundwater pressures, UPL and HYD, were required for Eurocode 7.
4 Wide range of particle sizes	Wide range of particle sizes causes a wide range of permeability so dissipation of pore pressure may take a short or long time. Hence need to consider both short- and long-term situations, i.e. undrained and drained conditions. Unique feature of geotechnical designs.
5 Inherently variable	The inherent variability of soil properties is usually much greater than the variability in the permanent loads, e.g. load due to the weight of the ground. Hence partial factors on loads in Eurocode 7 are usually smaller than those in structural design, e.g. partial factors on permanent and variable actions in Eurocode 7 (DA1.C2) are 1.0 and 1.3 compared to 1.35 and 1.5 for structural design and larger partial factors are generally chosen for ground properties, e.g. 1.25 on $\tan\phi$, compared to structural properties, e.g. 1.15 on steel strength.
6 Spatially variable	Since soil varies spatially and the volume of soil involved in any design situation is much larger than volume of soil tested, it is not normally appropriate to select the 5% fractile of test results as the characteristic value, A special definition was required for the characteristic value of a soil property which is given below the table.
7 Ductile	Soil can undergo very large shear deformations before failure, much larger deformations than structural members, and still retain significant shear strength. This ductile nature is beneficial because when soil supports a redundant structure, areas that are

	more heavily loaded or weaker will yield, enabling load to be transferred away from those areas to the less heavily loaded or stronger areas and hence allowing partial factors on loads in Eurocode 7 to be less than in structural design
8 Dilatant	Coarse soils are dilatant and expand when sheared, exhibiting a peak friction angle, ϕ'_{peak} , which falls to a critical state or constant volume angle, ϕ'_{cv} when the soil is sufficiently sheared. It is important to consider the strain at failure and the strength that is available to prevent failure. Eurocode 7 states that the strength parameter values obtained from test results, whether peak, critical state or residual, shall be interpreted appropriately for the limit state considered.
9 Compressible	Soil is normally much more compressible and less stiff than structural materials and can undergo large deformations exceeding the limiting values for structures. The controlling criterion in many geotechnical design situations is limiting the deformations rather than preventing failure. Geotechnical designs are therefore often controlled by serviceability limit state (SLS) considerations rather than ultimate limit state (ULS) requirements
10 Non-linear and complex stress-strain behaviour	It is difficult to determine appropriate parameters and to model soil deformations so it can be difficult to predict deformation reliably. For some geotechnical design situations, ultimate limit state calculations may be carried out with appropriate partial to limit the mobilised shear strength and hence limit the ground deformations as well as prevent failure.

Table 1: Features of soil and consequence for Eurocode 7

it was necessary to define the characteristic value of a geotechnical parameter. The definition given in Eurocode 7 is that: *“The characteristic value of a geotechnical parameter shall be selected as a cautious estimate of the value affecting the occurrence of the limit state”*. Now geotechnical designers have a definition for the value of the soil parameter to be chosen for use in geotechnical designs. This was an important and innovative development because, prior to this definition in Eurocode 7, the value of a geotechnical parameter for use in design calculations had not been defined. Engineers had to use their judgement and experience with no guidance given by the existing codes of practice. Often geotechnical parameter values provided by the ground investigation were used without any consideration of the design situation and the relevant limit state.

Figure 9: Attendees at meeting in London in 1946 that established ISO

4. STANDARDS BODIES AND BENEFITS OF EUROCODES

4.1 Eurocodes under the European Commission

As the work on the Eurocodes increased, with more Eurocode parts being prepared, and as the number of countries in the European Union (EU), which had formerly been the EEC, increased, it became clear that the European Commission, as a civil service type of organisation, was not the appropriate organisation to develop and publish codes of practice for engineering design. This problem was reflected in the slow progress on the Eurocodes since the European Commission became involved in 1975 and the difficulties in obtaining agreement on the format of the Eurocodes and how they related to existing European and International standards. Hence, in 1989, the European Commission decided to transfer all the work on the further development of the Eurocodes to a standards organisation. Possible standards organisation standards were ISO and CEN.

4.2 ISO

The standards organization known today as ISO began in 1926 as the International Federation of the National Standardizing Associations (ISA). This organization focused heavily on mechanical engineering. It was disbanded in 1942 during the 2nd World War. The initial meeting to re-organize it under its current name, ISO or the International Organization for Standardization, occurred in 1946 in London when 65 delegates from 25 countries shown in Figure 9 met to discuss the future of international standardization. ISO officially came into existence in 1947. ISO is an independent, non-governmental international organization now with a membership of 165 national standards bodies. ISO is an independent, non-governmental international organization. The ISO name is not an acronym or initialism but is the same name in all languages. ISO is derived from the Greek word *isos*, meaning "equal".

Prior to 1981, ISO had started to draft a standard for geotechnical design. However, by 1981 this work had not been completed and had stalled. ISO, being an organisation with members throughout the world as well as in Europe, it was not considered suitable to be responsible for drafting European standards. Furthermore, standards published by ISO are voluntary

Figure 10: Map showing 34 CEN national members in blue and 16 affiliate members in purple

not mandatory for ISO members to adopt. For these reasons the European Commission decided to transfer the work of preparing and publishing the Eurocodes to CEN, the Comité Européen de Normalisation or European Committee for Standardization.

4.3 CEN

CEN was founded in 1961. It was logical for the Eurocode work to be transferred to CEN because the mission of CEN is to foster the economy of the European Union (EU) in global trading, the welfare of European citizens and the environment by providing an efficient infrastructure to interested parties for the development, maintenance and distribution of coherent sets of standards and specifications. The move to CEN occurred soon after the collapse of the regimes in eastern Europe, resulting in the removal of the Iron Curtain in 1989 and the re-unification of Germany in 1990. An important consequence of the move to CEN has been the involvement of all the CEN member countries, some of which are not members of the EU and some of which were formerly communist states in the eastern zone of Europe, in the development of Eurocode 7. CEN's now 34 national members work together to develop European Standards (ENs) in various sectors to build a European internal market for goods and services and to position Europe in the global economy. The 34 national members are the standardization bodies of the 27 European Union member states, 3 European Free Trade Association (EFTA) countries plus the Republic of North Macedonia, Serbia, Turkey and the UK shown in blue in Figure 10. CEN has 16 affiliate members shown in purple in Figure 10.

4.4 Eurocode development in CEN

CEN's work of preparing standards is carried out by technical committees (TCs). CEN has 443 TCs, most of which are active but some have been disbanded or are dormant. TC250 was established in 1990 to oversee the development of the Eurocodes when this work was transferred from the European Commission. The British Standards Institution (BSI) holds the secretariat for TC250

Figure 10: Participants at SC7 Working Groups meeting at the NEN, Delft in December 2019

and is able to do so because BSI, as the UK's national standards body, has remained a CEN member even though the UK left the EU on 31st January 2020. Subcommittee 7 (SC7) of TC250 is responsible for Eurocode 7 and is hosted by the Dutch Standards Body, NEN. Over the years SC7 has set up many Working Groups, Task Groups, Evolution Groups and Project Teams to prepare, review and revise Eurocode 7. These have involved mostly voluntary inputs from a very large number of geotechnical engineers – from consultants, contractors and research organizations and academia. Many Irish geotechnical engineers have been involved in SC7 activities since it started its work over 30 years ago. The last face-to-face meeting of SC7's technical Working Groups before the Covid 19 pandemic was held at the NEN office in Delft in December 2019. Figure 10 shows the participants at that meeting. Since then all the SC7 meetings have been held virtually on-line.

Once CEN took over the management of the Eurocodes in 1990, they progressed more rapidly. The pre-standard trial version of Part 1 of Eurocode 7, ENV 1997-1 Geotechnical design: General rules was published in 1994 with a design method involving three Cases A, B and C and partial material factors. There then followed a trial period during which there was considerable debate amongst the geotechnical communities in the CEN member countries about the design method in the ENV version of Eurocode 7. It became clear that while much of the text was acceptable, some countries were not happy and sought the inclusion of partial resistance factors as well as partial material factors. The EN version was then prepared and included three Design Approaches that allowed the use of partial resistance factors as well as partial material factors. The standard version of Eurocode 7 Part 1, EN 1997-1 received a unanimous vote of acceptance by the CEN member bodies in 2004.

4.5 EN Standards and Vienna Agreement

It was critical to receive the unanimous vote in 2004 for Eurocode 7: Part 1 in order to ensure the new code's success and acceptance by the construction industry as an EN standard throughout Europe. Once a standard is published by CEN as an EN, all the members bodies of CEN must adopt it as their national standard with national annexes giving the partial factor values to be used in their

countries and withdraw any competing national standards. Eurocode 7 is published by CEN as an EN and so the same standard is used for geotechnical design in all the CEN countries. In contrast, standards published by ISO are not mandatory, unless they are adopted by CEN and published as EN ISO standards.

In order to avoid duplication of standardization work, it was decided in 1991, under the Vienna Agreement, that when CEN and ISO both required a standard in a particular area, they would cooperate and not compete. There has been collaboration between CEN and ISO in the preparation of various standards to support the Eurocodes. As a result, a very large number of supporting standards for Eurocode 7 have been prepared collaboratively, mostly in the past 10 years, by the following CEN and ISO committees:

- CEN TC 341: *Geotechnical Investigation and Testing*
e.g.: EN ISO 22477-4: *Testing of piles: dynamic load testing*
- ISO TC 182 *Geotechnics*
e.g. EN ISO 14688 and 14689: Standards for the identification and classification of soil and rock

Some supporting standards have been prepared just by the following CEN TCs with no ISO involvement:

- CEN TC 288: *Execution of special geotechnical works*
 - CEN TC 396: *Earthworks*.
- Orr (2012) has listed and provided details about the supporting standards for Eurocode 7 in the *ICE Manual of Geotechnical Engineering*.

4.4 Benefits of the Eurocodes

In 2003 the European Commission published Guidance Paper L listing the intended benefits and opportunities of the Eurocodes as being to:

- Provide common design criteria and methods;
- Provide a common understanding regarding the design of structures;
- Facilitate the exchange of construction services;
- Facilitate the marketing and use of structural components and kits;
- Facilitate the marketing and use of materials and constituent products;
- Be a common basis for research and development;
- Allow the preparation of common design aids and software;
- Increase the competitiveness of the European civil engineering firms, contractors, designers and product manufacturers in their world-wide activities.

These benefits and opportunities have been achieved because the Eurocodes have been adopted in all the CEN member countries. This has provided a common understanding and also a common "language" for geotechnical design in Europe. There has also been considerable interest in the Eurocodes outside of Europe, particularly in Asia, Africa and Australia where some countries have either adopted the Eurocodes or aligned their codes to the Eurocodes.

5 REGULATORY BACKGROUND AND IRISH STANDARDS

5.1 CPD and the Eurocodes

In order to further its objective of removing the technical barriers to trade in construction products between the European Union member states, the European Commission passed the Construction Products Directive (CPD) in 1988. The CPD sought to "*ensure the free movement of all construction products within the European Union by harmonizing national laws with respect to the essential requirements applicable to these products in terms of health and safety*". The essential requirements to be achieved in the case of structures include that they have acceptable mechanical resistance and stability and are safe in use and in the case of fire. The Eurocodes serve as a means to prove compliance of building and civil engineering works with the essential requirements of the CPD.

The CPD was repealed and replaced by the Construction Products Regulation, which was passed by the EU Commission in 2011 and came into effect on 1st July 2013. An EC Directive is a legal act of the European Union that requires member states to achieve a particular result without dictating the means of achieving that result. An EC Regulation is a legal act of the European Union that becomes immediately enforceable as law in all member states simultaneously. Regulations can be adopted by means of a variety of legislative procedures depending on their subject matter. The reason given for the change was to simplify and clarify the existing framework and improve the transparency and the effectiveness of the existing measures.

5.2 Irish Building Regulations

In order to implement in Ireland the Construction Products Directive published in 1989, the first Irish Building Regulations were published in 1991 with the latest update in 2021. The stated aim of the Building Regulations is to provide for the safety and welfare of people in and about buildings. This is similar to the aims of the former construction bye-laws. They apply to the design and construction of a new building (including a dwelling) or an extension to an existing building and requirements for the foundations of buildings. Since the Eurocodes had not been published as EN standards by 1991, they are not referred to in the 1991 Building Regulations or associated Technical Guidance Documents. However they are referred to in the current (2012) Technical Guidance Document A to the current Building Regulations which states: "*The use of the Eurocodes referenced in this document is a practical guidance on meeting the Requirements of Part A*".

5.3 National Eurocodes Advisory Committee

When work began on the Eurocodes, Ireland did not have a dedicated national standards body. To oversee the development of the Eurocodes from an Irish perspective, the National Eurocodes Advisory Committee, NEAC, was established. The chairman of the NEAC was Nick Ryan of An Foras Forbartha, which was The National Institute for Physical Planning and Construction Research from 1964

to 1987. Trevor Orr and Eric Farrell, because of their work on Eurocode 7 and geotechnical design, were invited to be members of the NEAC in 1986. Eric Farrell was appointed Irish representative on CEN/TC250/SC7 in 1990. Nick Ryan was chairman of the NEAC until 1994.

5.4 National Standards Authority of Ireland

In the early 1990s work took place to form the National Standards Authority of Ireland, NSAI. As a result in April 1994, Douglas Burns from the embryonic NSAI was appointed secretary of the NEAC with Jim Harrington as chairman. Jim Harrington's area of expertise was structural timber. In 1996, the National Standards Authority of Ireland Act was passed. The NSAI formally came into existence in April 1997 and became Ireland's official standards body and member of ISO and CEN. Barry Smith from NSAI took over as secretary of the NEAC from Douglas Burns. In 2013, Yvonne Wylde took over from Barry Smith as secretary of NEAC. She established the Eurocode Consultative Committee (ECC), TC 15, in 2013 and Jim Mansfield was appointed chair. Ken Murphy succeeded Yvonne Wylde as secretary of TC 15 in 2018.

A sub-committee TC 15/SC7 Geotechnics was established to monitor the development of Eurocode 7. Eric Farrell was appointed chairman of this committee. The main role of this sub-committee was to prepare a national annex for Eurocode 7, Part 1, giving the partial factors to be used with geotechnical designs in Ireland. Part 1 with the Irish National Annex was published by NSAI in June 2007. It was decided no National Annex was needed for Eurocode 7, Part 2, which was also published in 2007. TC 15/SC7 has monitored and is continuing to monitor Eurocode 7, including the development of the second generation version. In 2020 David Gill succeeded Eric Farrell as chair of TC 15/SC7.

Being a member of CEN, NSAI publishes CEN standards as Irish standards with the prefixes with the prefixes I.S. EN or where they are CEN standards that have been published by CEN but prepared with ISO under the Vienna Agreement, they are published with the prefix I.S. EN ISO. For example Eurocode 7 - Part 1 and the standard for the dynamic testing of piles are published as:

- I.S. EN 1997-1
- I.S. EN ISO 22477-4

NSAI now publishes as Irish Standards a large number of CEN standards relating to geotechnical design, ground investigations and testing, execution of geotechnical structures and earthworks. Hence there is rarely any need now to refer to non-Irish standards, such as British Standards.

6. SPREAD FOUNDATION DESIGN EXAMPLE

The width, B of the square pad foundation for a building, shown in Figure 11, is to be determined to satisfy both the ULS and SLS requirements for a building to be built in Ireland. The embedment depth is 0.8m. The foundation support a central vertical load where the variable load is 0.25% of the permanent load. The characteristic values of the ground properties are: $c'_k = 0$, $\phi'_k = 35^\circ$, $\gamma_k = 22 \text{ kN/m}^3$

Figure 11: Spread foundation example

Figure 12: Design foundation width plotted against total applied load for three ULS Design Approaches and SLS

and $E_k = 20$ GPa. The maximum allowable settlement is 25mm. Since the building is to be built in Ireland, it must be designed using the Design Approaches permitted in Ireland and the partial factors given in the Irish National Annex.

The design foundation widths calculated using the three Design Approaches with the relevant partial factors given in the Irish national Annex are plotted in Figure 11. The design width calculated using the traditional global factor of safety of 3.0 is also plotted. The graphs in Figure 11 show that:

- The design foundation width is controlled by ULS for lighter loads, in this example for loads less than about 1000 kN
- The foundation width is controlled by SLS for larger loads since large volume of ground is loaded leading to increased settlement
- DA2 gives smallest, DA3 gives largest and DA1 intermediate ULS design foundation widths
- The traditional FOS of 3 gives the largest design foundation width and hence is the least economical design when bearing resistance controls.

7. SECOND GENERATION OF EUROCODE 7

7.1 Review and priorities for 2nd generation Eurocodes
CEN regularly reviews and updates its standards. In 2015-16 a systematic review was carried out of all the Eurocodes. Arising from this review it was decided to prepare a second generation of the Eurocodes with the following priorities identified:

- Improved ease of use, particularly for day-to-day calculations;
- Increased harmonisation through a reduction in National Determined Parameters;

- Strengthening the requirements for robustness, which are additional measures carried out to protect against unforeseen events and hence further ensure the safety and reliability of designs.

Robustness is defined in the draft head Eurocode prEN1990-1(2020) as “Ability of a structure to withstand unforeseen adverse events without being damaged to an extent disproportionate to the original cause”. Strategies given in the November 2021 draft of EN1997-1 for designing geotechnical structures for robustness are that they should include providing:

- Enough ductility and deformation capacity;
- Redistribution of load within the geotechnical structure to avoid sudden collapse;
- Increased resistance of identified critical elements within the geotechnical structure;
- Larger acceptable excavation tolerances;
- Extra drainage capacity by appropriate design of drainage systems;
- Measures to prevent scour leading to erosion of soil under and around a geotechnical structure;
- Restriction on future loads on the ground surface or the structure.

7.2 Priorities for 2nd generation of Eurocode 7

In addition to the priorities identified for the second generation of all the Eurocodes, the following additional priorities were identified for the second generation of Eurocode 7:

- Simplification of Design Approaches leading to Design Cases with combinations of partial factors;
- Reorganization of structure and presentation – more consistent sections;
- Better alignment with EN 1990;
- Improved reliability discrimination;
- Improved rules for groundwater pressures;
- Improved rules for common geotechnical structures and more calculation models;
- Improved rules for numerical methods;
- Improved rules for design involving rock and dynamic design.

7.3 Key changes in 2nd generation of Eurocode 7

The second generation Eurocode 7 is being reorganised from 2 into the following 3 parts and some of the content of the parts is listed:

- Part 1. General Rules
 - Close alignment with EN 1990
 - Reliability differentiation
 - Ground water pressures
 - Numerical modelling
- Part 2. Ground Properties
 - Concept of Ground Model
 - Derived values
 - Alignment with CEN TC 341 testing standards
- Part 3. Geotechnical Structures
 - Clause 4: Slopes, cuttings and embankments
 - Clause 5: Spread foundations
 - Clause 6: Piled foundations
 - Clause 7: Retaining structures
 - Clause 8: Anchors
 - Clause 9: Reinforced fill structures (new)

- Clause 10: Ground reinforcing elements (new)
- Clause 11: Ground improvement (new)
- Clause 12: Groundwater control (new)

7.3 Reliability of Eurocode 7 designs

The draft second generation version of Eurocode 7, prEN1997 has 34 references to reliability whereas the existing Eurocode 7 has just 5 references to reliability. The basic requirement stated in the current head Eurocode, EN 1990: 2002, and in the draft second generation head Eurocode, prEN 1990-1: 2020 is that “A structure shall be designed and executed in such a way that it will, during its design service life, with appropriate degrees of reliability and in an economical way sustain all foreseeable and specified actions ...”. Structural reliability is defined in prEN 1990-1 as the “ability of a structure or a structural member to fulfil the specified requirements during the service life for which it has been designed”. Notes to this definition state that “Reliability is often expressed in terms of probability of exceedance” and that “Reliability covers safety, serviceability and durability of a structure”. prEN 1990-1 gives target values for the reliability index β related to the probability of failure for different Consequence Classes. However, it is not expected that β values and reliability analyses will be used for Eurocode designs; they are intended mainly for code calibration. prEN 1990 states that “The reliability required for structures within the scope of this document shall be achieved by design in accordance with the Eurocodes”. This is demonstrated by paragraph 4.2.1(4) of prEN 1997-1 which states: “The verification of limit states by any of the methods given in 1) (i.e. by calculation, testing, prescriptive rules and Observational Method) shall provide a level of reliability no less than that required by EN 1990-1”. More information about how the safety and reliability of geotechnical designs are being honed in the second generation of Eurocode 7 are given in Orr(2019).

7.4 Reliability differentiation

Reliability differentiation is defined in prEN1990-1:3.1.2.24 as “measures intended for the socio-economic optimisation of the resources to be used to execute construction works, taking into account all the expected consequences of failure and the cost of the construction works”. Reliability differentiation is achieved in prEN 1997-1 by the requirement in 4.1.2.3(1) that “Geotechnical structures shall be classified into a Geotechnical Category (GC) that combines the complexity of the ground and ground-structure interaction (Geotechnical Complexity Class) with the consequence of failure (Consequence Class) of the structure”. Currently classification of a design into a Geotechnical Category is optional. However with the second generation, the use of the Geotechnical Categories as reliability differentiation will be a requirement.

To ensure the appropriate level of reliability required by EN 1990-1, 4.2 is obtained, prEN 1997-1: 4.1.2.3(3) requires that the Geotechnical Category shall be used to specify the extent and amount of the following measures to ensure the appropriate level of reliability required by prEN 1990-1 is achieved:

- Measures to achieve appropriate representation of parameters for design, including appropriate ground investigation, validation of information from Ground Investigations and Design Model;
- Measures to achieve accuracy of the calculation models, interpretation of the results and validation of the models;
- Measures to prevent errors in design and execution, and the occurrence of gross human errors, including designer qualifications and experience; quality management measures, and amount and type of reporting
- Measures to ensure appropriate implementation of design including supervision; inspection; monitoring and maintenance.

An assumption in all the current Eurocodes is that “structures are designed by appropriately qualified and experienced personnel”. Similarly Annex D.4(2) of prEN 1990-1 states that “the personnel responsible for the design of a structure should have appropriate qualifications and experience, depending on the consequences of failure of the structure and the complexity of its design”. This implies that, for geotechnical designs, the qualifications and experience should be related to the Geotechnical Category. However prEN 1990-1 does not state what constitutes appropriate qualifications and experience but leaves those to be determined nationally.

Fintan Buggy led a committee of the ISSMGE that drafted minimum qualifications and experience for personnel involved in the design of structure in different Geotechnical Categories This was adopted by SC7 as Annex D of a draft of prEN 1997-1. However, this led to considerable debate within TC250 and the wider Eurocode community as it was argued that it was not appropriate for design standards to specify required qualifications and experience. A vote of CEN members on whether or not to include specific requirements for qualifications and experience of personnel in the different material Eurocodes, such as in Annex D of prEN 1997-1, and whether or not to include general requirements for qualifications and experience of personnel in Annex B of prEN 1990-1, took place in November 2021. Regarding the first question, of the 25 who voted, 9 were in favour of including specific requirements but 15 were against and so that proposal was defeated and hence Annex D has been omitted from prEN 1997-1. Regarding the second question, 16 were in favour of retaining general requirements, 7 were against and there was one abstention, hence Annex B has been retained in prEN 1990-1.

in order to have the professional qualifications and experience of those involved in geotechnical projects assessed and recognised, a register of geotechnical engineering professionals (RoGEP) was established in the UK. This register is being supported by the Geotechnical Society of Ireland and Engineers Ireland enabling geotechnical engineers in Ireland also to have their qualifications and experience assessed and recognised.

7.5 Key dates for 2nd generation of Eurocode 7

The second generation of all the Eurocodes are being prepared to coordinated and strict schedule The key dates for the preparation and publication of the second generation of Eurocode 7 are:

- October 2020 – January 2023 – Work by SC7 Task Groups to:
 - o Review draft documents;
 - o Prepare design examples to test code and its Ease of use;
 - o Prepare guideline documents;
- November 2021 – Latest draft documents of Parts 1, 2 and 3 issued;
- September 2022 - December 2022 – prEN Enquiry period with prEN available for public review;
- January 2023 – March 2024 – Comments resolution, text finalised and translated;
- April 2024 – June 2024 - Formal Vote on EN 1997;
- March 2026 – All Eurocode parts to be available to NSBs for NA preparation. It is hoped that Eurocode 7 parts will be available by late 2024 or early 2005. Then NSAI needs to prepare Irish NAs for Parts 1, 2 and 3;
- 30th September 2027 – Last date for NSBs to publish 2nd generation Eurocodes with their NAs leading to the co-existence period;
- 30th March 2028 – Date of Withdrawal (DoW) of existing Eurocodes.

Countries are free to publish the Eurocodes with National Annexes whenever they are ready. Some countries may publish the Eurocodes with their national annexes earlier than others. Some countries may publish all the Eurocodes at the same time (big bang approach) or in stages. NSAI plans to publish all the 2nd generation Eurocodes at the same time. There will be a coexistence period when either version may be used. The minimum coexistence period, October 2027 – March 2028, is 6 months is very short. NSAI is therefore planning a coexistence period of 12 months and hence aims to publish the Irish versions of the Eurocodes with their national annexes by March 2027. If NSAI receives the three Eurocode 7 parts by late 2024 or early 2025, this would provide a two and a half or three year period to prepare the National Annexes before March 2027.

8. CONCLUSIONS

To understand how geotechnical design in Ireland and Europe has advanced with Eurocode 7, the situation prior to Eurocode 7, i.e. prior to 1981, when work started on Eurocode 7 was examined and it was found that then:

- There were no Irish standards for geotechnical design;
- There was no dedicated national standards body in Ireland;
- British codes of practice and standards were mainly used for geotechnical design in Ireland;
- Separate codes were used for different geotechnical structures;
- There was no consistency between structural and geotechnical design codes;
- There were only bye-laws in three urban areas with regulations for geotechnical designs

- European countries had their own standards based on national practices and ground conditions;
- There was little involvement of Irish geotechnical engineers in Europe.

The situation regarding geotechnical design now in Ireland and Europe since Eurocode 7:

- Geotechnical design in Europe has been harmonised with all CEN countries using the same code for geotechnical design published as their national standard;
- Geotechnical design has been harmonised with structural design through the adoption of:
 - o A common design language in the limit state design method,
 - o Consistent safety requirements and partial factors;
- Eurocode 7 provides a single code for all the different types of geotechnical structures, rather than separate and different codes for each geotechnical structure as formerly;
- Eurocode 7 is supported by a large number of CEN standards for ground investigation, testing and the execution of geotechnical work.

Other advances in geotechnical design and benefits due to Eurocode 7:

- It provides a definition for the value of a geotechnical parameter to be selected for use in a geotechnical design. This is a novel feature and based on reliability theory aiming at achieving a target reliability;
- It is a flexible code, allowing the use of partial material or resistance factors within the limit state design framework with ;
- It provides for reliability differentiation through the use of Geotechnical Categories that are a combination of the Geotechnical Complexity Class and the Consequence Class which involve the following different types of measures:
- It uses the Geotechnical Categories to specify the following measures to ensure the level of reliability required by prEN 1990-1 is achieved:
 - o Measures to achieve appropriate representation of parameters for design;
 - o Measures to achieve accuracy of the calculation models used and the interpretation of their results;
 - o Measures to prevent errors in design and execution and the occurrence of gross human errors;
 - o Measures to ensure appropriate implementation of design according to procedures specified in the project documentation..
- It is accommodating scientific advances, e.g. in numerical analysis, reinforced fill structures and ground improvement
- It has brought together a large number of geotechnical engineers from across Europe in the development of Eurocode 7
- It has facilitated Irish geotechnical engineers to work in Europe and European engineers to work in Ireland.

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